

LINGUISTIC ASPECTS OF CULTURE REFLECTED IN A LITERARY TEXT

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ABSTRACT

The concepts of literature and culture are considered as closely connected notions. Culture affects the literary works or vice versa. As a consequent, the article investigates the relationship between culture and literary texts. The result of the research shows that linguocultures can be seen in any literary work and they show uniqueness of that works and nations.

Introduction. Language, literary texts and culture are interrelated. First of all, there are implications related to the teaching of language itself. For anyone who wishes to be able to interpret and understand meanings presented to him or her, the different cultural meanings embedded in language, the contexts and the cultural references of a language must necessarily be explored and, to the degree that it is possible, learned. In the same way, insight into the different aspects of situational and cultural contexts that come into play whenever language is used is an important factor in the foreign language learners ability to produce his or her own texts and to take part in communication situations.

Literature plays a prominent role in foreign language acquisition and it is revived as a prime part of language teaching with a view of linguistic and cultural aspects. Moreover it has a reinforcing outcome in a language class [5, p.181-194]. In English Language Teaching, Literature is commonly used for the enhancement of comprehending the language. Literature, a part of the whole humanity verges upon with universal issues. It paves the way to gain knowledge of multifarious structures of a language. Literature acts as a tool to widen some new methods and techniques in language teaching and learners can attain more benefits in the language learning and skills. Literature aids the learners to gain literary context and facilitate the same in their everyday usage and the characters influence and motivate to overcome various hindrances. It imparts their communicative skill of the language. Vocabulary, dialogues, poetry and prose helps the learners to communicate the language by using the new words. Literature lifts the learners to develop analytical skills. It facilitates the learners to get familiar with universal issues and motivates to read. According to Povey's observation "literature will increase all language skills because literature will extend linguistic knowledge by giving evidence of extensive and subtle vocabulary usage, and complex and exact syntax" [4, p.268-274]. Learning a language through literature enables the learners to be more creative and insightful.

Samovar, Porter and Stefani define culture as the deposit of knowledge, experience, beliefs, values, actions, attitudes, meanings, hierarchies, religion, notions of time, roles, spatial relations, concepts of the universe, and artifacts acquired by a group of people in the course of generations through individual and group striving [1, p.57-64].

This definition shows that culture is seen as something which is acquired or learned, and passed down from one generation to the next. Culture is seen as having to do with the material productions through which a group of people represents itself ('artifacts'), but the definition focuses first and foremost on people's knowledge, beliefs, attitudes, ways of thinking, behaving and remembering. In linking culture to 'a group of people', the definition indicates that culture is shared by the members of a particular community, and that one community is, somehow, different from another in terms of culture.

The notion that language and culture are closely linked together stems from the awareness that nature has no 'natural structure' from which language draws its meanings passively [3, p.37-84]. Rather, it is language that provides us with a classification of phenomena and experience and a system of categorization that make the world around us manageable. Our thoughts are not prior to language and language is not just a useful device we use in order to express them, but language is the very thing that makes thought possible.

The anthropologist Edmund Leach says that this world is a representation of our language categories, not vice versa. Because my mother tongue is English, it seems self evident that bushes and trees are different kinds of things. I would not think this unless I had been taught that it was the case [2, p.179-185].

The study of the literary text as a source of culture, an expression of national character and mentality of one or another people is increasingly attracting the attention of representatives of modern humanitarian science in the text as a unit of culture. The last time is characterized by rapid development of research in the field of language and culture, where language is considered as one of the forms of reflection of culture.

The following example from S.Maugham's "Theatre" illustrates the role of stylistic devices in expressing the cultural concept LOVE. The main character of the novel, Julia, paradoxical though it may seem, lives on the stage and plays in life. The given below dialogue between Julia and her son tells us about the latter's disappointment with his first love affair. Julia is upset. With enthusiasm and affection does she explain to her son what love is:

She gave him a little smile.

"And you really think that was love?"

"Well, it's what most people mean by it, isn't it?"

"No, they don't, they mean pain and anguish, shame, ecstasy, heaven and hell, they mean the sense of living more intensely, and unutterable boredom; they mean freedom and slavery>; they mean peace and unrest".

Here the concept LOVE is presented in a condensed, aphoristic form. The utterance contains a convergence of stylistic devices (gradation, antithesis, metaphor, epithet and others), which convey a set of conceptual features constituting the frame structure of the concept. It can be illustrated by the following diagram:

It is interesting to note that both positive and negative features are presented in contrast expressed by antithesis: heaven and hell, freedom and slavery, peace and unrest. The combination of the opposed and incompatible conceptual features and their complex interaction specify a deep-lying cognitive structure of the analyzed concept.

The influence of culture on literary texts in Russian language can be seen from the following example. Conditions of the feast and cuisine of the imperial time can be found in many literary works of the 19th century: "Eugene Onegin", "War and Peace", "Dead Souls" etc. The execution of the traditional Russian feast is described in great detail, which gives us the opportunity to compile a comprehensive visualization of what is happening in the dining room, as well as the kitchen, of the manor estate. It should also be noted that extent of a meal adequately showed the wealth and position of a nobleman. Therefore, the feast was one of the many pleasures in the life of a nobleman.

Phillip Vigel clearly illustrates the tableau culture of the nobility. Vigel argues that in order "to judge the unpretentiousness of the way of life of the Penza nobles at that time, one must know that none of them had faience, all were served clay and Murat (to glaze) dinnerware (although at least a few people did not sit down at a table without 24 dishes, soup, jellies, cooks, cakes). Only Mikhail Ilich Martynov, the owner of 1000 souls, more than the other hospitable and luxurious, had half a dozen silver spoons; they were put in front of honorable guests, while others had to be content with tin. "We can clearly see how the social status affected even the distribution of silver and tin spoons in a noble environment, and also notice what a varied menu was present even among middle-class nobles.

Conclusion. Literary texts are the basis of the influence of culture. Reading literary texts helps the learners to develop speaking and listening skills. Further, it improves pronunciation. Pronunciation can be the focused and judged before, during, or after the reading process. They assist and speed up the expansion of communication skills. It motivates the students to accomplish a clear conception of a work's intrigue and a deeper notion and perception of its characters. Through literary texts we can improve our

reading ability, analyzing the text and comprehending the passage and understanding of other cultures. It improves our organizational skills and critical thinking. Literature helps the students to deepen the writing skills and it clearly reflects in their original work especially the content, theme, organization, and style. This shows that literature acts as a tool to learn the subject easily, to promote critical thinking and to develop skills.

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